

MOTION MEASUREMENT WITH A MULTI-CHANNEL SAR

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the use of a Multi-channel SAR (MSAR) system for the characterization of scene motion. A ground based MSAR system (the NRL FOPAIR) is used to study system parameter sensitivities and an airborne MSAR is proposed. Our efforts demonstrate the advantages of using an MSAR for both determination of motion and removal of motion-related distortions and smearing in SAR imagery.

Index Terms— Synthetic Aperture Radar

1. INTRODUCTION

In general, single aperture SAR processors do not distinguish target motion from the relative motion between the sensor and stationary scene content. This ambiguity leads to motion related artifacts in processed imagery. A Multi-channel SAR (MSAR) system, in which the channels are arranged along the flight direction, is unique in its ability to characterize target motion against the background scene/platform relative motion. The time-sequence of images produced by the swept phase centers of an MSAR result in an animated representation of the scene with the added benefit of correcting for motion-induced distortions, thereby improving image fidelity. To date, the hardware complexity and processing horsepower required by MSAR systems have severely limited this technology. Recent advances in RF hardware miniaturization and increases in computing power now make MSAR systems feasible. An experimental foundation is now needed to fuel MSAR development. In this effort we exploit the unique capabilities of our own hardware, the NRL FOPAIR and NRL SAR systems, to provide this foundation. The FOPAIR system is currently a ground based MSAR containing up to 128 channels that can be rapidly sequenced to emulate an airborne MSAR with virtually any desired number of channels and range-to-platform-velocity ratio. Furthermore, such a system can be mounted on an aircraft to enable the collection of data over a large angle for each aperture. Such a system has the capacity to produce high spatial and temporal resolution imagery, allowing high-order scene (or target) motion determination and/or artifact removal capabilities. In this work, we demonstrate the MSAR advantage using our ground based FOPAIR system and propose a hardware configuration for in-flight NRL FOPAIR experiments to be done in fall 2014.

2. APPROACH

Our approach will be to use the unique ability of the NRL FOPAIR to emulate a wide variety of SAR collection parameters to explore the capabilities and limitations of MSAR systems. The FOPAIR data will be used to examine processing options and tradeoffs between spatial resolution and temporal resolution and provide a guide to the configuration of an airborne prototype for further future investigation which will then deal with the added complication of platform motion.

The NRL FOPAIR is an X-band (9.85 GHz) fully polarimetric, 200 MHz bandwidth (0.75m resolution) modular system capable of collecting up to 128 receive channels along its length (See Figure 1a). The collections can be repeated indefinitely to produce a 2-dimensional space-time matrix of pulses. An airborne MSAR can be emulated for a variety of plane speeds and MSAR channels by selecting a portion of the FOPAIR data as shown in Figure 1b.

The collected datasets can be processed in a number of ways to generate a velocity map and high fidelity images of the scene. Here we use a FOPAIR collection of a small boat travelling along scan direction at a speed of 12kts. This work provides an in-depth study of the robustness of processing techniques extending earlier work by Sletten [1].

The simplest use of the data is to process each scan into an image and then measure the motion from frame to frame to determine a speed for a bright target. Because each scan line is collected so rapidly, the smearing due to ocean wave motion is negligible, but the downside is that the resulting images have very low azimuth resolution. Nevertheless, using this approach we simulated MSAR systems with from 8 to 64 channels and found that even for an MSAR system with only 8 channels, a reasonably accurate speed can be estimated.

Another approach to velocity estimation which also provides high-fidelity image reconstruction is the Velocity SAR (VSAR) method proposed by Friedlander and Porat [2][3]. With this approach each channel is processed into an image giving the full azimuth resolution available for a SAR. This

Figure 1. The NRL FOPAIR (a) and resulting space-time pulse matrix (b) created by scanning along the receivers repeatedly.

leads to an image stack of length M (where M is the number of channels) that is then VSAR processed. The VSAR technique starts by a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) up through the stack to separate pixels by radial velocity creating a velocity stack. The images in the velocity stack will have targets that are shifted by a known amount (the well-known train-off-track shift of their radial speed multiplied by the range over platform speed ratio). After removing that shift the images are recombined to generate the high fidelity image. A search for the peak intensity along each pixel will also provide a radial speed estimate map. The scheme is illustrated in Figure 2.

This process can be done for a variety of emulated platform speeds (and corresponding range over platform speed ratios) to determine the robustness of the VSAR technique. Figure 3 shows the resulting VSAR image reconstruction for a range of platform speeds. Our results indicate that even for unrealistically large platform speeds, the VSAR method

performs reasonably well. In addition we have computed the VSAR images using 8, 16 and 32 channels and find that the resulting reconstructed images have similar fidelity as the corresponding fast-scan images.

Figure 2. VSAR processing starts with complex image stack, then FFT up through each pixel to generate a velocity stack. Next shift each image by a known amount and recombine to generate products.

Figure 3. VSAR processing of emulated MSAR system using a variety of platform speeds. The top row shows the emulated SAR images from one channel for five different platform speeds. The bottom row shows the VSAR reconstructed images.

The results of our testing show considerable gain in performance can be achieved even for a much smaller MSAR array size than FOPAIR. With this in mind we chose to construct a 32-channel MSAR, consisting of two banks of 16 channels each. This was the largest number of channels that could reasonably be flown and was sufficient to provide significant velocity resolution. To improve the system still further we will use two transmitters on either end of the array, effectively doubling the number and total width of possible phase centers (and halving the minimum detectable velocity). Such a system provides up to 64 velocity bins from about 1 to 80 m/s. It should be noted that if we separated the two 16 banks of channels a lower minimum speed could be achieved, but this introduces non-uniformity and complexity in processing. Our initial system will keep them adjacent.

3. CONCLUSION

We have examined the potential for motion measurement of an emulated MSAR system using the ground based NRL FOPAIR. Our preliminary results for a variety of platform speeds and channel numbers show that the MSAR provides a robust system for generating high fidelity images and velocity maps even for a low as 8 channels. Our analysis indicates that a proposed 32 channel MSAR system with two transmitters on either end will provide a system with practical utility for the measurement of typical boat and ship motions.

4. REFERENCES

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